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**A Brief Survey of the Great Postmodern Philosophical
Contributions**

Introduction

The crisis of modern philosophy began, perhaps, at the moment when the moderns proposed, or conceived ideas about the unknown to men about men that neither the traditions of particular sciences, nor religious moral traditions could resolve, that is, 'the will' in the existence of life against 'reason'. Likewise, it would become dark what would be the possibility of the impossibility of reaching either by philosophical means, i.e., metaphysical, or epistemic-exact means, in short, a *Veritas Aeterna* and Absolute Truth. Men threatened by uncertainty, that is, by being unable to be certain of anything, or to truly know anything according to reason and, above all, concomitantly with the death of God enunciated by logic, historical, exact and physical epistemes would lead men either to the denial of the value of life, or what would be left for them would be to end it in all its known forms! The certainty that the nature of man possessed in its given constitution at all times, as long as men were

men, a 'will', which was, finally, endowed with 'instincts' that would govern the destiny of all their respective activities or that, at least, would strongly influence their results, was something terribly threatening.

I

Of the issues that dismayed Modernity, philosophies focused on issues that were of the total tyrannical domination of Christian scholastics, but it was from Arthur Schopenhauer onwards that the issue of the crisis of humanism became evident. Many would say that Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel was the driving force behind the end of Modernity, creating with his system of the history of consciousness the last great system attempting to safeguard in a single system all the supposed truths prior to René Descartes and all the Enlightenment that preceded him. However, I think that Hegel *only* tried to systematize or to logicize and try to say in totalizing formulas what and in what essentially all those who preceded him had true consciousness; in short, everything that he would interpret and agree with, that is, what they would be aware of as being true. The supposed description of the history of the Absolute Spirit has an undemonstrated premise: that a limited man is certain about the current history - in which he is present - of the 'World Spirit' which he says is his interpretation of the history of consciousness. And as far as Hegel is concerned, he interprets in universal history 'the universal judgment', taking a motto from Schiller: this is the idea that is proclaimed in the first edition of his *Encyclopädie*

der philosophien Wissenschaften im Grundrissen, published in Heidelberg in 1817. Hegel believes in the history of humanity's progress as a process of the Absolute Spirit taking on "consciousness of freedom", he proclaims that universal history is "the authentic theodicy" and the only reason to give meaning to the struggles and conflicts, to the "pain" and to the "seriousness of the negative" that are typical of the historical process. This reflection, in the midst of the crisis of Enlightenment humanism, only continues the Christian dream of redemption and paradise on Earth, but now through secular political-state conflicts. Schopenhauer, on the other hand, speaks of the essence of "divine justice", which, when clarified, sublimates all false appearances of disharmony and injustice; thus, he proclaims: "If it were possible to place all the pain of the world on one side of the scale, and all the guilt of the world on the other, the scales would certainly be balanced."² As we know in *Die Welt als Wille and Vorstellung* was published a year after Hegel's Heidelberg *Enzyklopädie* and states that it is not universal or world history (*Weltgeschichte*), but the world itself (*Welt*) that is the universal judgment (*Weltgericht*). It is necessary to focus attention on the important reinterpretation of the word "theodicy" (in Hegel's language) made by Schopenhauer who calls it "divine justice", which does not occur in the historical process and socio-political changes that the world carries out, but is present in the world as it is, without the intention of remaining at the level of appearances, but reaching the essence. Schopenhauer, above all, sees pain and suffering in this world as inevitable results of the objectives of the character of men and of the actions of other organisms as a fruit of the essence of the world, that is, the will. Friedrich Nietzsche,

¹ Hegel, 1956a, pp. 298-9 (*Enzyklopädie der philosophischen Wissenschaften im Grundrissen*, 1817, § 448).

² Schopenhauer, 1976-82 a, pp. 480-4

however, as we will see, treats this supposed “divine justice” with ironic tones, although he draws inspiration from it.

II

For Nietzsche, then, the idea that the “so-called universal history” that he ironizes in his work *Die Geburt der Tragödie aus dem Geiste der Musik* (GT , 7 and 15; I , 56 and 100) and his private correspondence (B , II , 1, p. 190)³ had become a “arrogant metaphor” (C, 1; I , 759)³ and more than “divine justice” what was now generally spoken of was worldly “eternal justice.” This “eternal justice” before whose “tribunal” of the world the Greek state found “justification” despite its “naïve barbarism”, the war, slavery and pain it brought about (C, 3; I , 771 -2); for him, then, starting with Schopenhauer among others, the ideal of “universal history” dissipates, theodicy ends.

III

In place of theodicy, therefore, there is cosmodycy, and this is a category that was coined in a letter of 1872 (B , II , 2, pp. 534) by Erwin Rohde, a friend of Nietzsche, which was developed by the latter completely in *Die Geburt*. Therefore, one of Schopenhauer’s merits to the postmoderns, in my understanding, was to provide the

³ The acronyms B and C refer to the private correspondence of Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche.

conceptual bases for this category in which the nature of all reality is explained, founded on the conflicts between opposites, and which is *war* and all real conflicts, *in a sui generis and comprehensive* sense, that form the basis of everything that exists and is real. The analysis of the myth of ΠΡΟΜΗΘΕΥΣ (*Prometheus*) reveals the origin of all conflict in societies where, on the contrary, the interdependence of the possibility of cultural creation and, therefore, of civilization, requires the sacrifice of a social *stratum* so that the works of aesthetic, physical and exact epistemes are possible; so that then a noble class of men can make philosophy, art, science and politics. For a culture to flourish and be magnanimous, worthy of the stages of men's suffering in the world, with great works, there must always, necessarily, be a class of creative masters-of-themselves, and a class of slaves that is the driving force and workers of society. On the contrary, The Christian *Peccatum Originale*, although denied by Hegel as a doctrine that impedes the advancement of the consciousness of the absolute spirit, is the seed of revolutionary causes, or rather, which is the same as the moralist revolts that suppose that there is a redemption for all the suffering of these existences, whether in a world transcendent to this one, or in this one. The seed of the myth of paradise-on-Earth and the overcoming of the 'criticism-of-the-valley-of-tears' (as Karl Marx calls 'divine-justice') is the hope that history can come to an end in which man's evil existence would finally be corrected, that the world would be corrected and equality and peace would reign on Earth. However, as we can see, this hope is false for Nietzsche, insofar as 'worldly justice' is eternally the same in every actuality. The 'worldly justice' that men accept is always the same, because it is founded, so to speak, on sacrifice and *war* as a broad conflict; this is, therefore, the 'eternal justice' of all cultures and civilizations. There is therefore no teleologically universal Supreme Good that 'must' be fought for so that history

evolves and tends towards the freedom of all, that is, to fight against those and their works that are masters-of-themselves.

III

The solipsistic and pessimistic character is intrinsically subjectivist and these philosophies that preceded Nietzsche always presupposed, to different degrees, an internal spiritual essence that would be an 'I in itself' the foundations of reason and of all knowledge; that, finally, all Cartesian post-cogito philosophies fall into the same error in having faith in "consciousness" as the source of discernment of what is "apparent" or "essential", or between "false" or "true", or even between "illusory" or "real". Even though the entire Cartesian definition depends intimately on "*de omnibus dubitandum*", his "universal doubt", there is a gross error in making the existence of a 'thinking "I"' a factual one, a mere little "ego" that would be a *causa prima* of something "external" and, therefore, extensive and proper to accidents. The "I" as the existing causative essence of the activity of "thinking" is a postulate and belief in an "immediate certainty" presupposed as factual; now, that which thinks simply presupposes something that thinks, but not a *subjectum* as *qualitas occulta* that is the "cause" of thought; even to assume that something existing thinks is, in itself, a mere supposition, an *ad hoc hypothesis* not proven by thought. Even if one says "something thinks, therefore it thinks" - *Es denkt, so denkt es* - hence, nothing is immediately known, or verified beyond thinking. Furthermore, that which thinks, tautologically, thinks, therefore, nothing is immediately deduced as existing - this is perhaps, in reality, a postulate impossible to prove -; thus, "consciousness", and "ego"

are a mere illusion of grammatical origin in which *Jenseits von Gut und Böse* and *Wille zur Macht* concluded correctly.

For Nietzsche, his enemies even became his teachers, and in the times of the “philosophical workers” such as Immanuel Kant, Hegel and the neo-Kantians (such as Schopenhauer), the profound critical attempt against all philosophy of subjectivity and fundamentalisms, or foundationalisms based on the dichotomies of consciousness (mind-spirit [*Geist*]) and body, and the deep doubt as to the naïveté of philosophy in wanting to describe the history of the world with ultimate objectivity, became clear. The Schopenhauerian will was perfumed and rationalized so that it could be, demonized, said as the character of organisms distorting the objectivity of reason as moral, even as an antithesis of moral. For Nietzsche, on the contrary, morality (a world-falsifying reason) is nothing more than a mere and desperate consequent form of the will to power of certain men to injure and control aspects of reality - other men - by affirming their supposed moral superiority of self-blame and the blaming of others. While all the *übermensch*, the affirmers of the will, as it is given to them in their respective projects, designs and desires, affirm it as an eternal ‘yes’; for him these men, therefore, are the great affirmers of life. The old conceptualized assumptions such as ‘essence’ and ‘accident’, ‘soul’ and ‘body’, ‘cause’ and ‘effect’, the subjectivist foundationalisms are liquidated as mere constructs of perspectives that equate different metonymized metaphors - as concepts are defined by him

in *Über Wahrheit und Lüge im außermoralischen Sinne* (1873) -. From the conceptual illusory categorical mesh it is derived the eternal anthropocentric delirium of the subjugation of nature to man, when the world and not man makes the destiny of everything that exists. It is from a philosophy like this that Martin Heidegger could try to found a philosophy of the future, other philosophers could also do so, as long as they understood it; they understood the real need of Western civilizations to overcome subjectivism, the great illusions that deny life, nihilism.

On the Character of Objectivity in “*Sein and Time*” by Martin Heidegger

Heidegger’s proposal for a ΓΙΓΑΝΤΟΜΑΧΙΑΠΕΡΙΤΗΣΟΥΣΙΑΣ (*γίγαντομαχία περι τῆς ουσίας*)⁴ of *Sein and Zeit* as a philosophising about the “question of the meaning of being in general” („*Frage nach dem Sinn von Sein überhaupt*“) is, first of all, an attempt to philosophize beyond the limits of subjectivist metaphysics. He says that it is said by the philosophical tradition that “being” is the most universal concept and, therefore, the most empty and obscure; although, likewise, “being” is the fundamental concept of ontology and of all ontologies, thus being concomitantly of all the particular scientific ontic areas of the ‘being’ of the entities of these particular epistemes. Precisely because “being” is

⁴ από Πλάτωνα. ΣΟΦΙΣΤΗΣ, 246ε.

ΤΟΟΝΕΣΤΙΚΑΘΟΛΟΥΜΑΛΙΣΤΑΠΑΝΤΩΝ (τὸ ὄν ἐστὶ καθόλου μάλιστα πάντων) and because the 'entity' - whatever the entity in question - occurs in ΟΥΤΕΤΟΟΝΤΕΝΟΣ (οὔτε τὸ ὄν γένος), then, Heidegger argues that "being" is not any particular entity and that it cannot be defined by any more general concept of any kind of entities. However, because "being" is a *transcendens*⁵, a transcendental concept which transcends all the most general "real concepts" of gender, it is, therefore, the most vague, the undefined and, above all, the concept that no philosopher before Heidegger defined and explained its connection with all categories, or inferior genera of beings. Medieval philosophy, mainly Thomistic and Scotistic, did not arrive at a clear definition of principle and Hegel conceptualized and defined it, basically, as "the indeterminate immediate" in the later categorical explanations in his *Wissenschaft der Logik*, putting it and leaving it aside, denying the uniqueness of "being" in the face of "the multiplicity of real "categories". Therefore, Heidegger thinks that this is a primordial philosophical question that needs to be answered, although first the "question of being" itself has to be defined.

III

The Heideggerian *Dasein* could be clarified when one unfolds the meaning of the structure that determined the word itself; philologically, *Dasein* is derived from the meaning said in "*In der Welt sein*" which can be translated as being-in-the-world; therefore, no being is primarily outside or inside the world, but is in the world. Nietzsche would say that all events (entities, in Heidegger's case) are proper to the world, as different manifestations

⁵ Being and Time (by Martin Heidegger) Editora Dozes, 4th Edition (First Chapter - Necessity, structure and primacy of the question of being, § 1.)

and characters of the world that presents itself to us exactly as it is - the world-there -; and yet, for Heidegger, who means the essence of beings in the world, their most general and fundamental being, the primacy of 'the question of the being of the entities' presupposes that there is an answer to the essence of *Dasein*. Heidegger, however, tells us that the questioning of the questioned, of the interrogated, asking oneself about what it is like the "being" a specific entity, or what it is like to "be" of beings in the world in general, is openness, a type of generosity, an original way of asking oneself about beings - intending the things themselves -, it is authenticity. *Dasein* would also be, therefore, the opening of asking oneself and not saying 'what' things - entities - are in themselves, that is, when we predicate them, when we entify them; thus, if *Dasein* is being-in-the-world, it is also world and the particular way of knowing an entity, the known is, therefore, the ontic. It is said, consequently, that the essence of *Dasein* is existence, the *Sein*, therefore, has to exist and the mode of giving of the *Sein* is presence, that is, *Dasein* is the way in which the operation of the utensils presents itself, *Dasein* is, therefore, an original experience and the mode of being of the operation of entities - insofar as they are utensils -, insofar as they are-at-hand, to manuality (*zuhandenheit*). I interpret the opposite of this as the 'simply given being', 'the ontic' - *vorhandenheit* -, that which does not have the way of being *Dasein*, therefore, 'the known', 'the predicate' and 'the categorized'.

VIII

Given this polysemy of investigative definitions to define *Dasein*, defining it is a closure to the question of the meaning of the being of entities, an inauthenticity: to return to the things themselves is, therefore, to intend to the portal for a new beginning. To describe 'how' the operation of the utensils takes place, for example, it is necessary to deal with concepts of a range of unique utensils that will never fully capture the unexpected becoming of the operation of the utensils, and from what seems logical to me to think, there is no "specific, particular genre" of the 'operation of the utensils', since *Dasein* is the original experience of the presence of the entities to be operated. I ask myself, then: if Heidegger answered the question of the meaning of being, did he find the essence of the *Dasein* of entities, of the world? And if he did not answer the question, would he not have ontologically failed to propose a true *ΓΙΓΑΝΤΟΜΑΧΙΑΠΕΡΙΤΗΣΟΥΣΙΑΣ*, an architectonic of "being"? If so – although it is known that historically this is not the case – then a new beginning through new portals and a continuous questioning of the essence of *Dasein* is not possible. Therefore, the necessary crises in the particular sciences, the crises of the fundamental concepts, could not thus be the beacon of measurement and revolution as such through the respective crises in them but rather through permanent absolute truths, which would deny the authentic character of *Dasein*. It seems to me, however, that it did not sufficiently respond and solidly establish as desired the category of "being", as initially proposed in the work, because the task of describing the uniqueness of each operation in each respective original, authentic experience, for example, the *Dasein* of men, seems truly endless in such a way that one cannot end and complete all the connections of the question of the meaning of being in an architectural ontological system. Therefore, when I think about the objective of

the work *Sein and Zeit*, what was intended to be answered was the theme of the question of the meaning of "being" in a type of non-subjectivist post-Nietzschean philosophizing and as the philosophy that I want to construct is not based on any type of purely subjective, illusory considerations, I cannot much less accept ontologies of subjectivity and, therefore, I come to the conclusion that the area of ontology has no objectivity whatsoever in questioning itself more about "the meaning of "being" in general". It is not even necessary to comment on Paul Sartre's philosophy, since it accepts and advocates, decadently, a subjectivism that, even worse, is truly anthropocentric.